

1 **Seismicity and hydro-mechanical coupling along strike-slip**
2 **faults in flat-and-ramp structures : the case of the Vuache**
3 **Fault in the Annecy Molasse Basin (French western Alps)**

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7
8 **SUMMARY**

9 This study aims to understand the recurrent seismicity that occurs in a limited volume
10 along a major fault in the French western Alps, the Vuache Fault, which crosses the geo-
11 logical Jura in a flat-and-ramp zone. In 1996, an M5.3 earthquake occurred near Annecy
12 (France), located at a depth of approximately 2 km. In this article, we analyze the seis-
13 micity that has occurred since then and calculate the seismic velocity variations at local
14 permanent seismic stations. We show that, while the magnitude and focal mechanism of
15 the 1996 M5.3 earthquake indicate that the process was indeed tectonic in origin, the
16 duration of the Omori decay of its aftershocks, their migration, the variations in spring
17 flow, the existence of repeated swarms, the seasonal variations in seismic velocity and

18 their relationship to rainfall and seismicity show that the continuation of this seismicity is
19 linked to the pressurization of fluids in a deep, fractured aquifer connected to the surface.
20 This aquifer appears to be limited to the sedimentary formations. Earthquakes, especially
21 during the M5.3 aftershock migration, reach the depth of the Triassic gypsum. The after-
22 shock sequence occurred in two different phases: an initial phase lasting around ten days,
23 during which the earthquakes did not show any migration but rather a random spatial
24 distribution, and a second phase showing a clear migration, suggesting a fluid diffusion
25 process. During this last phase, the hydraulic diffusivity of the aquifer was calculated
26 and estimated at around 1 m²/s. The same order of magnitude was obtained by using the
27 correlation between seismic velocity variations and rainfall. This is a high value, close
28 to those found during man-made fluid injections. This aquifer forms a confined, pressur-
29 ized reservoir between two thrusts in the regional flat-and-ramp structure. The scenario
30 described in this article could be found, at various scales, in flat-and-ramp regions where
31 tectonic stresses are sufficient to generate seismicity.

32 **Key words:** Micro-seismicity, Alps, fluids, hydro-mechanical coupling, earthquake mi-
33 gration, seismic velocity variations, flat-and-ramp, Vuache Fault, Annecy

34 1 INTRODUCTION

35 Seismicity in western continental Europe is moderate and sparse, and large-magnitude earthquakes are
36 not frequent. This makes these earthquakes difficult to study; it is also rare to have enough information
37 to understand them in depth. Nevertheless, detailed studies are essential to their comprehension.

38 The north-west of the French Alps is affected by such a moderate seismicity. In this area, around
39 180 earthquakes of intensity IV to VII have been reported since the Middle Ages, mostly in the Pre-
40 Alps, which cover most of this area. The hypocentres calculated for instrumental seismicity show
41 depths ranging from 2 to 10 km (SisFrance 2025).

42 On July 15, 1996, the Epagny-Annecy earthquake occurred on the Vuache Fault, a left-lateral
43 strike-slip alpine fault. Although superficial (2 km deep, Thouvenot et al. (1998)), this earthquake
44 reached a 5.3 local (LDG) magnitude (ISC and NEIC : $M_w = 4.5$). Its focal mechanism (Thouvenot
45 et al. 1998) was left-lateral strike-slip at short period, and normal at long period. The rupture of this
46 earthquake was relatively complex for an earthquake of this magnitude, involving two sub-events

47 (Courboulex et al. 1999). Several hundred aftershocks were recorded in the days and months that
48 followed; about 400 of them were located (Thouvenot et al. 1998).

49 Following this earthquake, local and national seismological networks (SISMALP, RAP, RESIF,
50 now EPOS-France) were extended, and local data were accumulated during 30 years, showing some
51 continuous earthquake activity. In the meantime, new methods have been developed. This article anal-
52 yses these data and synthesises them with older data and results, to provide an update and a better
53 understanding of the origin of this seismicity.

54 Intraplate seismicity is often linked to the presence of fluids, although this seismicity is generally
55 deeper than that of the Epagny-Annecy earthquake, and in a different context (see, e.g., Costain et al.
56 (1987); Reyners et al. (2007); Balfour et al. (2015); Wehrens et al. (2016); Gardonio et al. (2018)).
57 In the western Alps, 150 km southeastwards of Epagny-Annecy, the 2-10 km deep seismicity of the
58 Ubaye area located below the flysch nappes is also attributed to fluids (Jenatton et al. 2007; Leclère
59 et al. 2013; Thouvenot et al. 2016; De Barros et al. 2019). Seismicity induced by forced-fluid injections
60 also occurs at comparable depths and geological contexts (see, e.g., Deichmann & Giardini (2009);
61 Diehl et al. (2017)). For all these reasons, it was a natural step to investigate now the possible role of
62 fluids and geological structures in the local, shallow, Epagny-Annecy seismicity.

63 **2 GEOLOGICAL, SEISMOLOGICAL AND HYDROGEOLOGICAL CONTEXT**

64 From east to west, the western Alps comprise four units: the external crystalline massifs, the subalpine
65 massifs, the Molasse Basin and the geological Jura (Figure 1). The region studied is located in the
66 Molasse Basin, between the subalpine massifs and the geological Jura, north of Annecy. The Molasse
67 Basin is a flexural foreland basin. It extends around the Alps, covering more than 700 km between
68 Chambéry in France and Linz in Austria. It is filled with molasse, a detrital formation resulting from
69 the Tertiary erosion of the Alps.

70 Beneath the Tertiary molasse in Annecy lies the Dauphinois sedimentary sequence (Figure 2),
71 comprising locally a succession of Mesozoic limestones (especially Urgonian (Lower Cretaceous),
72 and Tithonian (Upper Jurassic)) and marls from the Cretaceous and Jurassic periods. They overlie the
73 Triassic formations, comprising a layer of gypsum and marls, resting on the granitic continental crust.
74 The Urgonian limestones, which outcrop on the summits, are karstic.

75 The study area includes the Mandallaz Mountain thrust fold, a Jurassic-style ramp anticline. It is
76 separated from a similar anticline, the Age Mountain thrust fold, by the Vuache Fault (Figure 3). This
77 is one of the region's north-west/south-east-trending left-lateral strike-slip faults. The northernmost
78 thrust fold structures in this region (Salève (Figure 1)) moved faster than the southernmost blocks
79 (Mandallaz, Age), so that the punching of the European plate by the Adriatic microplate not only

Figure 1. Simplified structural map of the western Alps. Dashed lines represent the directions of the cross-sections: A (Figure C.1) and B (Figure 4). The study area is represented by the black solid rectangle.

80 caused a WNW/ESE shortening in that region, but also a NNE/SSW extension that formed small
 81 extensional structures like the Annecy basin, filled by the Tertiary molasse.

82 The Vuache Fault has been active since at least the Triassic period. It is synchronous with the
 83 thrust faults of the Mandallaz (NE compartment) and Age (SW compartment) mountains, the former
 84 having formed at a faster rate than the latter. The NE thrust compartment (Mandallaz) shows internal
 85 deformation (Crêts and Machurettes hills; see, e.g., Guglielmetti et al. (2022), Figure 3).

86 The NE and SW compartments show a vertical offset of about 600 m (SW compartment higher,
 87 Figure 2). Thouvenot et al. (1998) showed that the Vuache Fault at Epagny has a dip of 70° towards the
 88 northeast. Seismic profiles crossing this fault show a loss of coherence corresponding to a destructured
 89 zone, with a flower structure, over a width of around 1 km (Delataille (2015), p.147-149).

90 The Annecy region has been the site of several historical earthquakes (Table A1), notably in 1839
 91 (a swarm of eight earthquakes between 7 and 27 August, with an earthquake of intensity VII on
 92 11 August) and in 1879 (four earthquakes between 25 July and 15 October, with an intensity III-
 93 IV earthquake in a swarm on 27 September). It is noteworthy that the seismicity felt mentions the

Figure 2. Sedimentary sequences of the Annecy Molasse Basin close to the Annecy town, in the SW (a) and NE (b) compartments of the Vuache Fault, showing the Tertiary molasse and the Mesozoic limestones and marls lying above the Triassic gypsum. Note the vertical offset of about 600m between the two compartments.

94 existence of swarms, which are often associated to a progressive rupture under the effect of fluid
 95 pressure.

96 Delacou et al. (2004, 2005) and Mathey et al. (2021) showed that the Annecy region was lo-
 97 cated in an area where the present stress state currently led to left-lateral strike-slip deforma-
 98 tions, as demonstrated by the mechanism at the epicentre of the M5.3 earthquake in Epagny on 15/07/1996
 99 (Thouvenot et al. 1998), with a NNE-SSW extension component and a WNW-ESE compression com-
 100 ponent. Thouvenot et al. (1998) also mentioned that the focal mechanism inferred from surface wave
 101 inversion by Bock (1997) was a normal fault.

102 Thouvenot et al. (1998) carried out a precise location of the aftershocks of this earthquake. They
 103 showed that 96% of them occurred in the 3.5 km thick post-Triassic cover, mainly in the Upper Jurassic
 104 (Tithonian) and Lower Cretaceous (Urgonian), two layers of massive limestone. The aftershocks are
 105 distributed in two swarms along the Vuache Fault (Figure 3), with the mainshock occurring close to
 106 the southern end of the NW swarm. The SE swarm is closer to the surface than the NW swarm, and
 107 its depth corresponds to that of the Urgonian limestones. A volume remains without aftershocks to the
 108 SE of the mainshock, between the two levels highlighted by the aftershocks (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Map of the Annecy Molasse Basin showing the cartographic trace of the Vuache left-lateral strike-slip fault (dashed blue line) and the main local tectonic features (from Guglielmetti et al. (2022); black dashed lines: subvertical faults; black indented lines: thrusts), the M5.3 1996 Epagny mainshock (black star), the aftershock locations (coloured dots) after Thouvenot et al. (1998), and the location of springs. BR (red): Bains-de-Bromines thermal springs; CR (blue): Chez-les-Roux spring; F (blue): Fontanettes spring; CB (blue): Combe-à-la-Biche spring; TB (blue): Trou de Boubioz sublacustrine spring. Colour of the dots indicates the aftershock depth. The dashed red contour line and the pink shaded zone show the aseismic zone between the NW (deeper) and the SE (shallower) earthquake swarms. The five black triangles represent the local stations of the RAP accelerometric network, installed in 2012-2013.

109 Courboux et al. (1999) studied the source of the M5.3 Epagny earthquake using empirical
 110 Green's functions calculated from well-recorded aftershocks close to the mainshock. They showed
 111 that the mainshock could be decomposed into two sub-events and that the rupture propagated towards
 112 the south-east, along the Vuache Fault. Three interpretations of this kinematics could be made, de-
 113 pending on the respective positions of the initiation and termination points of the rupture in relation to
 114 the aseismic volume (Figure 3). Either these two points were north of this volume, or they were south
 115 of it, or they were on either side of it. In the latter case, the rupture would have propagated from the
 116 northwestern segment to the southeastern one, with the first sub-event triggering the second without

117 necessarily rupturing the intermediate volume. The source of this earthquake is therefore complex,
118 despite its intermediate magnitude.

119 Another remarkable feature of this seismic sequence noted by Thouvenot et al. (1998) is the in-
120 crease in flow rate (approximately x5) of the thermal springs at Les Bains de Bromines (Figure 3),
121 located on the Vuache fault trace at the foot (500m altitude) of the Mandallaz mountain, close to the
122 northern end of the aftershock swarm. Conversely, the non-thermal water spring known as Chez-les-
123 Roux spring (Figure 3), located at an altitude of 600m, dried up after the earthquake; it only returned
124 to its initial flow rate four months later. This spring is, with the Combe-à-la-Biche spring (900m alti-
125 tude), one of the overflow springs located at the (impermeable) molasse/(karstic) Urgonian limestone
126 interface, close to the top of the Mandallaz mountain thrust folds. The location (altitude and geolog-
127 ical position) of the Chez-les-Roux and Combe-à-la-Biche springs shows that the Urgonian karstic
128 aquifer is saturated. The differences in altitude between these two overflow springs show that there are
129 different compartments in the aquifer, probably separated by a fault such as the one indicated at this
130 location by Guglielmetti et al. (2022).

131 Thouvenot et al. (1998) also reported that the flow rate of sublacustrine springs in the north of
132 Lake Annecy (at least one is known at Trou de Boubioz, 80m below the surface of the lake, located
133 close to the intersection of the Vuache Fault and the Semnoz thrust, (Figure 3)) increased after the
134 earthquake, but this information could not be verified. The altitude of the surface of the lake and the
135 Annecy-Epagny plain is about 450m.

136 The hydrogeology of the region was described by Carfantan et al. (2003) in discussing the origin
137 of the thermal springs of Aix-les-Bains (Figure 4). The water from these springs comes from the top
138 of the thrust folds in Urgonian karst limestone, which allows infiltration. It then follows the limestone
139 layer deep underground until it is stopped by a thrust, where it rises to the surface. In Aix-les-Bains,
140 drilling has revealed thermal water (temperature and composition) at a depth of 2.2 km, at the base of
141 the Tithonian limestones. This type of hydrogeological structure is proposed for the Jurassic thrust
142 folds in the region.

143 **3 DATA**

144 Three sets of data were used in this study to characterise the seismic activity and medium in the
145 Epagny region, affected by the M5.3 earthquake on 15 July 1996. The first set consists in the locations
146 of aftershocks of this earthquake, recorded by the temporary post-seismic response network from 17
147 to 29 July 1996 (Thouvenot et al. 1998). The second set is the catalogue of earthquakes recorded by
148 the permanent networks (SISMALP between 1995 and 2013, then RESIF, now EPOS-France-RLBP)
149 in the same region between 1995 and 2024. The third set concerns the waveforms recorded by local

Figure 4. WNW-ESE cross-section (B in Figure 1) of the flat-and-ramp Jurassic structure at Aix-les-Bains, 40 km SE to Annecy, showing the thermal water circulation in the karstic limestones from the summit to the springs. Adapted from Carfantan et al. (2003).

150 stations of the permanent accelerometric network (RAP, now EPOS-France-RAP) between 2012 and
151 2021.

152 3.1 July 1996 M5.3 aftershock location data

153 The location data for the aftershocks of the M5.3 earthquake on 15 July 1996 come from recordings
154 made by the temporary post-seismic response network described in Thouvenot et al. (1998). On 15 and
155 16 July, 16 short-period digital stations (2 Hz seismometer, GPS-synchronised), including four three-
156 component stations, were installed in an area of approximately 12x12 km centred on the mainshock
157 epicentre (Figure 5 of Thouvenot et al. (1998)), enabling locations to be determined from 17 July at
158 8:25, until 29 July at 3:34 p.m.. Several hundred aftershocks were recorded, and 346 of them were
159 located using a modified version of the HYPO71 programme taking into account altitude, and a local
160 velocity model (Table 2 of Thouvenot et al. (1998)). Here we use the complete set of 346 aftershocks
161 located by Thouvenot et al. (1998), which have an average location uncertainty of 260 m horizontally
162 and 335 m vertically, an average RMS of 30 ms and an average epicentral distance to the nearest
163 station of 2 km.

164 **3.2 SISMALP/RESIF/EPOS-France permanent network earthquake locations, 1995-2024**

165 In this study, we also use the catalogue of earthquakes recorded by the french Alps permanent net-
166 work over the period 1995–2024 (Langlais et al. 2024). This catalogue was established over two main
167 periods: 1987-2013, using SISMALP, a network of up to 48 stations in triggered mode equipped with
168 1-Hz vertical seismometers; this network was gradually replaced from 2014 by RESIF/EPOS-France,
169 a continuous recording network comprising, since 2020, 17 3-component broadband stations, 37 ac-
170 celerometers and 7 short-period stations in the Alps, north of 44° (Langlais et al. 2024). In the new
171 system, detections and picks are made automatically from continuous data streams using SeisComp,
172 with manual review/validation of seismic events, which are then located (see Langlais et al. (2024)
173 for details). In the Annecy/Epagny region, this network comprised 5 accelerometric stations (Figure
174 3; see section 3.3 below).

175 **3.3 RAP seismic waveform data, 2012-2021**

176 After the occurrence of the 1996 M5.3 Epagny earthquake, an accelerometric local network, part of
177 the permanent national accelerometric network (RAP), was installed. It was made fully operational
178 from mid-2012, and comprised 5 stations (Figure 3). These stations were equipped with low noise
179 Kinematics EpiSensor Triaxial ES-T accelerometers, with an extended bandwidth (DC to 200 Hz).
180 Among them, one (OGEP, Epagny) was located at the M5.3 epicenter close to the center of the after-
181 shock area, and another (OGME, Meythet) was installed at the southern end of this aftershock area.
182 Three-component seismic signal was continuously recorded from mid-2012, sampled at 100 Hz, and
183 stored at the RESIF data center.

184 **4 METHODS**

185 **4.1 Coda wave interferometry - Computation of seismic velocity variations**

186 Lobkis & Weaver (2001, 2003) showed that Green functions can be retrieved by correlating the diffuse
187 acoustic wave fields recorded at two receivers. A Green function (GF) is the impulse response of an
188 elastic medium between two points. Campillo & Paul (2003) and Campillo & Shapiro (2004) extended
189 this finding to seismology and demonstrated that the GFs are related to the cross-correlation functions
190 (CCF) of long time series of ambient seismic noise or coda waves of earthquakes recorded either by
191 distant seismic stations or by different components of a single station (De Plaen et al. 2016). Moreover,
192 by comparing CCFs obtained at different time windows, it is possible to detect tiny modifications of
193 the medium in which waves propagate (Sens-Schönfelder et al. 2006; Brenguier et al. 2008).

194 These modifications are generally variations of the velocity of seismic waves which produce delay

195 in travel times. Better sensitivity to velocity changes is obtained by analyzing the coda of CCFs. The
 196 relative variations of travel times are related to the relative variations of velocity as $\frac{dt}{t} = -\frac{dv}{v}$. Because
 197 the velocity changes are generally not homogeneous in the whole ellipsoidal volume sampled by the
 198 coda waves, they are referred as Apparent Velocity Variations (AVV). These can be estimated by
 199 either the Moving Window Cross-Spectral analysis (Poupinet et al. 1984; Brenguier et al. 2008) or the
 200 stretching method (Lobkis & Weaver 2003; Sens-Schönfelder et al. 2006).

201 4.2 Location in depth of the seismic velocity variations

202 The AVV depend on the frequency band of the coda waves used for their calculation. Because the coda
 203 is dominated by Rayleigh waves, the distribution in depth of the velocity perturbation can be estimated
 204 by inversion of the relation:

$$\frac{dv}{v}(f) = \int K(z, f) \frac{dv}{v}(z) dz \quad (1)$$

205 where z is the depth, f is the frequency and K is a sensitivity kernel. This kernel is the derivative of
 206 the Rayleigh wave phase velocity with respect to the S wave velocity (Herrmann 2013; Lesage et al.
 207 2014). The inversion is linear and can be written as:

$$Gm = d \quad (2)$$

208 where m is the vector of velocity perturbations as a function of depth $\frac{dv}{v}(z)$, d is the data (AVV(f))
 209 and G is the Jacobian matrix containing the partial derivatives. To estimate m , we follow the approach
 210 used by Lesage et al. (2014) based on Tarantola & Valette (1982), considering that the a priori model
 211 for the velocity perturbation is null:

$$m = C_m G^t (G C_m G^t + C_d)^{-1} d \quad (3)$$

212 where C_m is the a priori covariance matrix, C_d is the data covariance matrix, and G^t the transpose
 213 of G . The kernel K used to compute G is calculated for each frequency using the derivative of the
 214 Rayleigh wave phase velocity with respect to the S wave velocity (Herrmann 2013). The a priori
 215 covariance matrix expresses the physical correlation between the velocity variations at two different
 216 depths z_1 and z_2 :

$$C_m(z_1, z_2) = \sigma^2 e^{-\frac{|z_1 - z_2|}{\lambda}} \quad (4)$$

217 where σ is the a priori standard deviation for $\frac{dv}{v}(z)$ scaling the physical velocity perturbations around
 218 the (null) a priori model, and λ is the depth correlation length. The choice of these regularization
 219 parameters σ and λ is made through the use of a L-curve (Hansen 1992).

Figure 5. Cumulative number of earthquakes $M \geq M_c = 1.2$ as a function of time in days (1995-2024). The blue diamond represents the M5.3 1996 July 15th Epagny mainshock, the green square represents the M2.7 2013 April 6th Meythet earthquake, and the red disk represents the first event of the 7-hour January 9-10, 2024 M1.2-1.5 earthquake swarm (5 events, followed by 8 M1.2-1.5 events on January 12-19th).

220 **5 RESULTS**

221 **5.1 Earthquake number time series**

222 Results of the earthquake detection and location from 1995 to 2024 allows the computation of the
 223 completeness magnitude $M_c \approx 1.2$, and the b-value $b \approx 0.9$ (Figure E.1) for this time period. The
 224 time series of earthquakes $M \geq M_c$ is represented Figure 5.

225 **5.2 Apparent velocity variations**

226 The Cross-Correlation Functions of seismic noise were calculated in the period 2012-2019 between
 227 the horizontal North and East components of the single stations OGEP (located at Epagny, close to the
 228 M5.3 main shock epicenter) and OGME (at the SE of the region of aftershocks).

229 We used the program MSNoise (Lecocq et al. 2014) with analysis windows of 30 minutes with
 230 50% overlap. We defined the reference CCF by stacking the CCFs over one year and the current
 231 CCF by averaging over a 14-day moving window. The AVV between the reference and the current
 232 CCFs were calculated using a window in the coda between 5 and 55s after the first arrival, in various
 233 frequency bands. The time shifts were calculated using the Moving Window Cross-Spectral analysis
 234 for samples with a coherence greater than 0.65, and by the stretching technique.

235 Their representation over one-year time periods at station OGEP (close to the M5.3 mainshock
236 epicenter) shows a remarkable seasonal pattern in the 1-2 Hz frequency band (Figure 6) : velocities
237 are lower during the first six months of the year, and higher during the last six months.

238 With the aim of estimating the distribution in depth of the velocity variations, the AVV were
239 computed in 81 one-octave overlapping frequency bands, between 0.1 and 3 Hz. The amplitude of
240 the seasonal velocity variations in each frequency band and for each year is taken as the difference
241 between the 90th and the 10th percentiles of the absolute value of the AVV. This procedure minimizes
242 the effect of eventual outliers. The average amplitudes and corresponding standard deviations of the
243 AVV as a function of the frequency are displayed in Figure 7. They can be thought as a dispersion
244 curve which presents a very smooth variation for frequencies above 0.5 Hz.

245 **5.3 1D inversion of apparent velocity variations**

246 The sensitivity kernels (equation (1)) were computed from the S-wave velocity and density models of
247 the Epagny basin (Figures B.1 and B.2).

248 The determination of the regularization parameters σ and λ of the inversion (equation 4) was
249 performed through a series of inversions. Following the L-curve criteria, the value retained for these
250 parameters is the best compromise between minimizing the norm of the regularized solution and the
251 misfit. We found the values $\sigma = 0.1\%$ and $\lambda = 100m$. Finally, the result of the inversion with these
252 values (Figure 8) is the distribution of the velocity variation as a function of depth. The restitution
253 index (Figure B.3) fluctuates around 1 down to 2 km depth, which indicates a good recovery in this
254 depth interval (Vergely et al. 2010).

255 **6 DISCUSSION**

256 A simple yet striking result introducing this discussion is found in the spatio-temporal distribution of
257 aftershocks following the Epagny 1996 M5.3 earthquake obtained from the locations of Thouvenot
258 et al. (1998), which shows migration over about 2-3 km from the mainshock location in 15 days in a
259 NW-SE direction (Figure 9).

260 During a rupture process, restoring equilibrium in the damaged and weakened medium requires
261 the redistribution of the highest stresses over a larger area or volume than before the rupture. This re-
262 distribution occurs through a process of transfer or diffusion (of stresses, fluid pressure, momentum),
263 without one process being exclusive of the others; it is likely that, depending on, e.g., fracturing, fluid
264 pressure and/or time period, one of these processes dominates the others. This transfer process controls
265 the spatio-temporal distribution of aftershocks. The transfer of elastic stresses from the mainshock has

Figure 6. Apparent relative variation in seismic velocity (AVV) measured at the OGEP station (Epagny), in %, in the 1-2 Hz frequency band (single-station, NE cross-component), as a function of time in days, over one year. The red line shows the daily average between 1 January 2013 and 31 December 2019; the other colour lines represent the seven annual AVV between these dates.

Figure 7. Amplitude of the annual AVV as a function of frequency, and error bars, for the OGEP/OGME station pair. Average of the NN and EE components over the 2019-2020 time period. The green curve represents the dispersion curve computed from the model found after inversion (Figure 8).

266 been invoked by, e.g., Harris (1998), Stein (1999), King & Cocco (2001), Steacy et al. (2005), Freed
 267 (2005), and Hardebeck (2020) to explain the short-term spatio-temporal distribution of aftershocks.
 268 Furthermore, Peng & Zhao (2009) showed that the radius of the early aftershock zone, which oc-
 269 curred within the first three days following the M6 mainshock in Parkfield, California, increases as
 270 the logarithm of the time since the mainshock. This growth is consistent with propagating afterslip,
 271 i.e. the diffusion of momentum. The diffusion of a fluid pressure disturbance in a porous and frac-
 272 tured medium has been invoked by Nur & Booker (1972), Shapiro et al. (1997), Shapiro et al. (1999),
 273 Shapiro et al. (2003), Miller & Nur (2000), Miller (2013), Miller (2020) and De Barros et al. (2021).
 274 In our case, it was both the migration of the aftershocks (Figure 9), the duration of their time series
 275 (Figure 5) and the S waveforms of local earthquakes (Figure 10) that prompted us to investigate more
 276 in detail the 1995-2024 earthquake number time series, the aftershock sequence, the seismic velocity
 277 variations, and the eventual storage, transfer and diffusion of fluids in and around the Vuache Fault.

Figure 8. Variation of the seismic velocity as a function of depth below the surface, and error bars, inferred from the 1D inversion of the AVV (Figure 7).

278 **6.1 Detailed analysis of the 1995-2024 earthquake number time series.**

279 Earthquakes recorded from 1995 to 2024 are mostly located in the Epagny plain (Figure 11), at the foot
 280 of the thrust fold of the Mandallaz mountain. Their extension is limited to the SE, north to Annecy,
 281 and to the NW, below the Mandallaz mountain. Most earthquakes are located in the NE compartment
 282 of the Vuache Fault. From 1995 to 2000, most earthquakes recorded by the permanent network were
 283 located around the 1996 mainshock. From 2010 to 2020, there were more earthquakes southeast of the
 284 mainshock. More recently seismicity has developed near the NW end (Figure 11).

285 Earthquake number time series from 1995 to 2024 (Figure 5) first shows that the post-M5.3 earth-
 286 quake rate regularly decreased during about 6000 days, that is more than 16 years, following an Omori
 287 law with $p \approx 1$ (Figure 12). By comparison, the 1994 M5.1 earthquake in Le Grand-Bornand (France)
 288 (Fréchet et al. 1996; Thouvenot et al. 1998), which occurred in the neighbouring western French Alps
 289 at 10 km depth in the granitic crust was followed by only 13 M-0.3 to 0.9 aftershocks in 15 days,
 290 and one M2.1 aftershock 13 months later. Miller (2020) shows that long time series of aftershocks are
 291 more likely to be produced by fluid pressure diffusion.

292 From 2012, earthquake rate increased again and produced a $20 M \geq M_c$ earthquake swarm from
 293 February to April 2013 (Figure 5), culminating with a M2.7 event on April 6th, 2013, located close

Figure 9. Map of the Annecy Molasse Basin showing the cartographic trace of the Vuache Fault (dashed blue line), the M5.3 1996 Epagny mainshock (black star), the aftershock locations (coloured dots) after Thouvenot et al. (1998), and the location of springs (see Figure 3 for spring details). Aftershock colour represents the time from mainshock date, in days.

294 to Meythet at 2 km depth. The earthquake rate then decreased during about 1000 days, and increased
 295 again, producing new swarms in June-July 2021 and January 2024 (Figure 5).

296 As noted by numerous authors (see, recently, Büyükakpınar et al. (2025); Raggiunti et al. (2023)
 297 and references therein), earthquake swarms are often related to an aseismic process: pore pressure
 298 change (Miller 2013), magma intrusion (Toda et al. 2002), slow-slip events (Holtkamp & Brudzinski
 299 2011), these processes themselves involving fluids. The increasing phase of the earthquake rate in a
 300 fluid-induced swarm has been modelled by the progressive damage of a finite-size resistant rock het-
 301 erogeneity by Got et al. (2024). This model follows Kachanov (1958, 1986) approach according which

Figure 10. Amplitude of the seismic waveform of a typical Epagny earthquake (February 16th, 2014, at 3:51) as a function of time, for the three components of the OGEP RAP accelerometric station. The red and green vertical lines represent respectively the P- and S-wave arrival times. S-waves are low-frequency whereas P-waves are high-frequency. Such waveforms (known as hybrid-frequency waveforms) are characteristic of hydrofracturing, due to rock brittle failure by pressurized fluids (see, e.g., Yu et al. (2021)). P-waves evidence brittle failure, whereas S-waves are simultaneously filtered at high frequency and amplified at low frequency by the resonance of a fluid-filled cavity.

302 resistant area/volume decreases during the damage process, the stress being transferred to the remain-
 303 ing intact area/volume. The stress increases and generates an increasing earthquake rate, following an
 304 inverse Omori law, up to the complete rupture of the finite area. The equilibrium is then restored by
 305 the redistribution of the stresses over a larger area in the damaged, weakened, medium. This complete
 306 process can be observed when it remains quasi-static. This is the case when it is induced by an incom-
 307 pressible viscous fluid. In this case the fluid pressure decreases sharply with each rupture/earthquake,
 308 because the rupture quickly creates a volume that is only slowly re-pressurised by the fluid (see, e.g.,
 309 the valve model of Sibson (1981), and more recently Marguin & Simpson (2024)). The process is
 310 therefore controlled by the fluid flow, and recalls the velocity-controlled rock mechanics experiments.

Figure 11. Map of the Annecy Molasse Basin showing the cartographic trace of the Vuache Fault (dashed blue line), the M5.3 1996 Epagny mainshock (blue diamond), the M2.7 2013 Meythet earthquake (green square), and all $M > 0$ earthquakes located using permanent seismic networks between 1995 and 2024 (coloured dots).

311 Finally, the fluid pressure favours the initiation of the instability; but it inhibits its propagation when
 312 fluid pressure decreases with the increasing volume. Pressurised fluids therefore favour quasi-static
 313 deformation processes, by means of a series of small earthquakes in an elastic-brittle medium. This
 314 frame may explain the small-magnitude earthquake swarms evidenced in the Epagny-Annecy area
 315 (Figure 5). Larger magnitude earthquakes involve the slow relaxation of tectonic stresses during the
 316 rapid weakening of a large rock volume.

317 **6.2 Detailed analysis of the Epagny 1996 M5.3 aftershock sequence**

318 Detailed analysis of the aftershock sequence shows two phases (Figures 13 and 14).

Figure 12. Cumulative earthquake number as a function of time in days from mainshock (1996-2012; day 1 - 6000), for earthquake magnitudes larger than the completeness magnitude $M_c = 1.2$. Blue: Earthquake number data. Magenta: Omori's model for $p = 1.07$ and $c \approx 4$ days.

319 During the first 10 days following the main shock, the sequence of aftershocks mainly affected the
 320 Epagny basin (north-eastern compartment of the Vuache Fault), but also spread in its south-western
 321 compartment and in the bedrock (Figure 13a). It was punctuated by the occurrence of a stronger af-
 322 tershock (M4.2) on 23/07/1996 (8 days after the mainshock). The distribution of aftershocks in the
 323 Epagny basin is organised into two separate patches (Figure 3), one to the NW of the main shock
 324 and the other to the SE, as already noted by Thouvenot et al. (1998) and studied by Courboulex et
 325 al. (1999). Within the NW patch and west of the Vuache Fault, the spatial distribution of earthquakes
 326 is mainly random (Figure 13). The M4.2 aftershock (day 8) immediately triggered a large number
 327 of small aftershocks, which occurred randomly over a fairly large area. Nevertheless, the SE patch
 328 showed some spatio-temporal migration during this period. Between the two patches, an aseismic
 329 zone persisted.

330 From day 11, the seismicity pattern changed considerably and became organised in time and space
 331 (Figures 13 and 14). It developed mostly along a subvertical fault plane and only in the north-eastern
 332 compartment of the Vuache Fault (Epagny basin); no earthquakes affected the granitic crust (Figure
 333 14). It clearly showed a spatio-temporal migration along a planar structure, with an aseismic zone
 334 around the mainshock (Figure 14b). The seismicity occurred in 10-hour swarms (Figure 13c). The
 335 latest earthquakes are distributed in the periphery, to the NW downwards and upwards, and to the SE
 336 mainly downwards, between the base of the Tithonian and the bedrock.

337 This result illustrates two possible regimes for the spatio-temporal distribution of seismicity.

338 (1) The first 10-day period is dominated by elastic interaction, i.e. the progressive transfer of
 339 stresses from damaged areas to more resistant areas. This interaction is responsible for the temporal

Figure 13. Map of the Annecy Molasse Basin showing the cartographic trace of the Vuache Fault (dashed blue line), the M5.3 1996 Epagny mainshock (black star), the M4.2 main aftershock (green star), and the aftershock locations (coloured dots) after Thouvenot et al. (1998). Aftershock colour represents the time from mainshock date, in days. (a) Before day 11. (b) From day 11. (c) Earthquake rate as a function of time, in 0.1 day unit. Black arrow indicates the time limit between plots (a) and (b).

340 clustering at the beginning of the sequence, then at the time of the M4.2 aftershock. This triggering
 341 can be dynamic and/or by static elastic interaction. It concerns small volumes already very close to
 342 rupture, which are randomly distributed, due to the distributions of the rock strength and the fluid
 343 pressure. No obvious large-scale migration is observed during this time period (Figure G.1).

344 (2) From day 11, the migration observed is characteristic of fluid transfer in a fractured medium,
 345 and of the reactivation of existing fractures by the fluid pressure. The computed migration velocity
 346 (Figure 15) is close to 0.7 km/day. This is a high value, since natural systems usually lead to migration
 347 velocities comprised between 3 and 100m/day (Danré et al. 2022). The value found here is closer to
 348 the 0.5 to 1 km/day found by Lengliné et al. (2017) during the Rittershoffen injections, performed for
 349 hydraulic stimulation.

Figure 14. NW-SE cross-section of the M5.3 1996 Epagny aftershock zone, showing the M5.3 mainshock (black star), the M4.2 main aftershock (green star), and the aftershock locations (coloured dots) after Thouvenot et al. (1998). Aftershock colour represents the time from mainshock date, in days. (a) Before day 11. (b) From day 11. Red, horizontal, dashed line indicates the top of the granitic crust. (c) Earthquake rate as a function of time, in 0.1 day unit. Black arrow indicates the time limit between plots (a) and (b).

350 **6.3 Analysis of seasonal variations in seismic velocities**

351 Calculations of apparent seismic velocity variations (AVV, see section 5.2) in the Epagny-Annecy
 352 area show seasonal variations with an average over 7 years of 0.1% for frequencies between 1 and 2
 353 Hz (Figures 6 and 7), which correspond to depths between 1 and 2.5 km below the surface (Figure
 354 8). This is the depth interval at which most earthquakes occur (Figure 14; Thouvenot et al. (1998)).
 355 Representing the number of earthquakes per month of the year (Figures F.1 and F.2) also shows a
 356 seasonal trend (though the number of earthquakes is low), with more earthquakes in the first half of
 357 the year when seismic velocities are low.

358 Numerous authors (e.g., Kachanov (1958), Kachanov (1986), Walsh (1965), Budiansky & O’Connell
 359 (1976), Bruner (1976), Cox & Meredith (1993), Heap et al. (2009, 2020)) show that the presence of
 360 cracks reduces the bulk and shear moduli, and the velocities of P and S waves. The existence of varia-
 361 tions in seismic velocities at depths of 1 to 2.5 km below the surface therefore suggests that there are

Figure 15. Distance between aftershocks and mainshock, in km, as a function of time in days from mainshock. Blue line: model for an earthquake migration velocity $V = 0.7$ km/day.

362 variations in the opening and area of fractures at these depths. The fact that they are seasonal, with
 363 minimum velocities (more open fractures) between February and July and maximum velocities (less
 364 open fractures) in September-October, suggests that at these depths (1-2.5 km) (i) the rock is fractured,
 365 (ii) a pressurised aquifer is present, and (iii) this aquifer is connected to the surface. This conjecture is
 366 strengthened by the correlation between variations in seismic velocities and rainfall (Figure 16). The
 367 fact that these seasonal variations have a zero mean also indicates that this aquifer is drained, and that
 368 the water supply fluctuates around the outflow rate.

369 The geological formations that are likely aquifers at 1-2.5km depth below the surface are the
 370 karstic Urgonian limestones, the Valanginian marl-limestones and the fractured Tithonian limestones
 371 in the Vuache Fault (Figure D.2). This possibility is consistent with the regional hydrogeological
 372 model proposed by Carfantan et al. (2003) (Figure 4). In this model, the aquifers are part of the ramp
 373 of the overlapping fold and are fed by meteoric water; the SW boundary of the aquifer corresponds to
 374 the Vuache Fault, whose vertical offset of 600 m places impermeable formations facing the aquifers.
 375 The fault therefore acts as a hydraulic barrier, preventing fluids from spreading south-westwards. A
 376 reservoir can therefore be formed in the karstic and fractured formations, which is pressurised by the
 377 water column contained in the aquifers. The molasse acts as a horizontal impermeable cover ('cap
 378 rock') and prevents water from rising vertically to the surface. This interpretation is consistent with

Figure 16. Blue curve: time derivative of the AVV measured at the OGEP station, as a function of time, for the year 2019; red curve: normalised rainfall ($\times(-1)$) measured at Meythet airport weather station, as a function of time. The two time series have been aligned after computing the 10-day time lag between them.

379 the spatial distribution of the seismicity, especially of the 1996 M5.3 aftershocks showing a clear
 380 migration (Figure 13b), which are confined in the NE compartment of the Vuache Fault.

381 **6.4 Constraining aquifer properties by using seismological observables**

382 *6.4.1 Estimating hydraulic diffusivity by using aftershock migration*

383 Representing the squared distance between aftershocks and mainshock as a function of time (Figure
 384 17) shows that the seismicity front may also propagate as the square root of time. This shows that it

385 is difficult to discriminate between a linear fluid transfer process and a diffusion process with these
 386 data; moreover, both processes can co-exist. This was already noted by Lengliné et al. (2017) for the
 387 Rittershoffen injection seismicity.

388 When a step pressure perturbation occurs in a saturated, isotropic and homogeneous poroelastic
 389 medium, three waves propagate: P and S waves, and an additional compression wave, which is a pore
 390 pressure diffusion wave in the poroelastic solid. This is a low-frequency wave, which is the solution of
 391 a Biot equation whose control parameter is the hydraulic diffusivity coefficient D . When this equation
 392 is solved, the distance r between the aftershocks and the source of the pore pressure perturbation (often
 393 taken as coinciding with the mainshock) can be expressed as a function of the time t (Shapiro et al.
 394 1997, 1999):

$$r = \sqrt{4\pi Dt} \quad (5)$$

395 By adjusting the squared distance reached by the aftershocks from the mainshock location as a function
 396 of time from day 11 to 14 (Figures 13 and 14), we can estimate D (Figure 17) during this period. We
 397 find a hydraulic diffusivity reaching 2 m²/s. For comparison, a diffusivity of 0.05 m²/s was found
 398 from Ubaye earthquake swarms (Jenatton et al. 2007), and 0.07 m²/s from the Rittershoffen injection
 399 seismicity (Lengliné et al. 2017). The relatively high diffusivity value we find in this study may be due
 400 to both the high permeability created by the intense fracturing occurring in the central reservoir in the
 401 first 10 days, and to the existing high permeability along the Vuache Fault in the NW-SE direction.

402 6.4.2 *Estimating hydraulic diffusivity by using seismic velocity variations*

403 Seismic velocity variations also provide opportunities to constrain the hydraulic diffusivity. The first
 404 opportunity is brought by comparing rainfall records and seismic velocity variations. Rainfall records
 405 are flow rate measurements. Seismic velocities vary with the volume of fractures, and therefore with
 406 the volume of fluid contained in the fractures when they are saturated. To compare seismic velocities
 407 and daily rainfall, either the daily rainfall must be compared with the time derivative of the calculated
 408 seismic velocity (Figure 16), or the seismic velocities must be compared with the cumulative rainfall.
 409 Figure 16 shows that these quantities are strongly linearly correlated, seismic velocity variations being
 410 delayed relative to rainfall by about 10 days. When averaged over several years (e.g. Figure 6), the
 411 random variations due to daily rainfall disappear and only the average trend controlled by temperature
 412 remains.

413 The 10-days time delay computed at the RAP seismic station OGEP can be used to constrain
 414 hydraulic diffusivity using equation (5), by considering that the step pressure perturbation is produced
 415 at the surface of the aquifer (top of the Mandallaz mountain) and propagates down to 1.5-2.5 km depth,

Figure 17. Squared distance between aftershocks and mainshock, in km², as a function of time in days from mainshock. Blue line: model for a diffusivity $D = 2 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$.

416 and 2-3 km horizontally, that is about 3 km in 10 days. From equation (5) we infer D close to $1 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$,
 417 an order of magnitude consistent with the estimation performed from aftershock migration.

418 Notice at that purpose that computation of seismic velocity variations and their correlation with
 419 rainfall time series may provide a simple and economical contribution to the characterisation of an
 420 aquifer.

421 *6.4.3 Checking orders of magnitude of fluid pressure variations needed to induce seasonal seismic*
 422 *velocity changes*

423 Nafe-Drake curve (Ludwig et al. 1970) approximation by Gardner et al. (1974) (see also Brocher
 424 (2005)) provides a simple relationship between P-wave velocity V and density ρ for sedimentary
 425 rocks, when $1.5 < V < 6.1 \text{ km/s}$:

$$V = a\rho^4 \tag{6}$$

426 where a is a constant. This could be written

$$\frac{V}{V_{ref}} = \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_{ref}} \right)^4 \tag{7}$$

427 using a reference velocity V_{ref} and density ρ_{ref} corresponding to a given, initial state.

428 Considering the macroporosity ϕ due to rock mass fracturing, and neglecting, for sake of simplic-

429 ity, the poral fluid content (porosity times fluid density), we can write

$$\rho = (1 - \phi) \rho_m \quad (8)$$

430 where ρ_m is the density of the rock matrix.

431 In that case $\rho_{ref} = (1 - \phi_{ref}) \rho_m$, and

$$\frac{V}{V_{ref}} = \frac{(1 - \phi)^4}{(1 - \phi_{ref})^4} \quad (9)$$

432 that is, for $\phi \ll 1$,

$$\frac{V}{V_{ref}} = \frac{1 - 4\phi}{1 - 4\phi_{ref}} \quad (10)$$

433 or

$$\frac{\Delta V}{V_{ref}} = \frac{-4\Delta\phi}{1 - 4\phi_{ref}} \quad (11)$$

434 Considering that $\Delta\phi$ corresponds to the variation of the volume v of the pores/fractures, $\Delta\phi = \frac{\Delta v}{v}$

435 and

$$\frac{\Delta v}{v} = -\frac{1 - 4\phi_{ref}}{4} \frac{\Delta V}{V_{ref}} \quad (12)$$

436 The variation in porosity causes deformation that can be considered small enough for the rock
437 to remain linearly elastic. In that case, overpressure in the pores/fractures is related to their volume
438 variation by

$$\Delta P = K \frac{\Delta v}{v} \quad (13)$$

439 where K is the rock mass bulk modulus. From equations (12) and (13), we can infer

$$\Delta P = -\frac{1 - 4\phi_{ref}}{4} K \frac{\Delta V}{V_{ref}} \quad (14)$$

440 Obtaining an order of magnitude for the fluid pressure from this relationship requires orders of
441 magnitude for each of its parameters.

442 The macroporosity ϕ_{ref} is the average effective porosity of the karstic fractured rock mass in the
443 initial, reference state. For epigenetic (drained) karst massifs, Worthington (1999) and Bonacci et al.
444 (2006) estimated porosity values between 0.1 and 1%, and Albert et al. (2015) reported values less
445 than 2%. Klimchouk (2007) reported values as high as 12% (with a mean value of 4%) for hypogenetic
446 (undrained) karsts. As a consequence, the term $1 - 4\phi_{ref}$ remains in the [0.5, 1] interval.

447 $\frac{\Delta V}{V_{ref}}$ is the relative variation in P-wave velocity. Brocher (2005) shows that the $\frac{V_p}{V_s}$ ratio is approx-
448 imately constant for $1.5 < V_p < 5$ km/s, so that the order of magnitude of $\frac{\Delta V}{V_{ref}}$ can be approximated
449 by the measured $\frac{\Delta V_s}{V_s}$.

450 Obtaining an order of magnitude for the fluid pressure from this relationship also requires an order
451 of magnitude for the bulk modulus, at the scale of the fractured rock mass. Hoek & Diederichs (2006)

452 and Heap et al. (2020) show that elastic moduli severely drop with fracturing, bulk modulus decreasing
453 to about 1 GPa for fractured rock masses. Though the real value of K cannot be known with certainty,
454 this order of magnitude leads to find a fluid overpressure variation in the [0.12, 0.25] MPa range in
455 fractures to explain the computed seismic velocity variation of 0.1%. This overpressure corresponds
456 to a seasonal fluctuation of about $\pm 10 - 25$ m of the water column, which seems a reasonable order of
457 magnitude in the karstic limestones of this region. The seasonal seismic velocity variation computed
458 is therefore compatible with a seasonal water table fluctuation.

459 **6.5 A simple hydro-seismo-mechanical model for the Epagny seismicity**

460 Seismic velocity variations, aftershock migration and local hydrogeological knowledge can be inte-
461 grated in a simple hydro-seismo-mechanical model.

462 Seasonal seismic velocity and seismicity variations, and correlation between variations in seismic
463 velocities and rainfall (section 6.3) suggest that at 1-2.5 km depth a pressurised and fractured aquifer is
464 present, and that this aquifer is connected to the surface. The primary aquifer, outcropping at the top of
465 the thrust folds (Montagne de la Mandallaz), is the karstic Urgonian limestone formation. This aquifer
466 is considered as saturated up to the molasse-Urgonian interface, as shown by the "Chez-les-Roux"
467 overflow spring.

468 The M5.3 1996 mainshock occurred at 1.5 km depth bsl, at the bottom of the Tithonian limestone
469 formation. It was followed by at least 400 recorded aftershocks, located mostly above the granitic
470 bedrock. These aftershocks show two different regimes: the first during the first 10 days, where the
471 seismicity occurred randomly around the mainshock and its main aftershock; the second, after day 11,
472 shows a clear and fast (0.7 km/day) aftershock migration along the Vuache Fault zone (diffusivity 2
473 m²/s).

474 These two different seismicity regimes may be understood as follows. The large number of earth-
475 quakes that occurred during the first 10 days in the aftershock area tended to weaken it, also increasing
476 its permeability (see, e.g., Simpson et al. (2001)). Stresses and pressure that were no more supported
477 by the rock mass were transferred to the fluid, increasing its pressure at depth. Miller (2008) shows
478 that high diffusivity (1-3 m²/s) is necessary for the delayed pore pressure variation to be high at depths
479 greater than 2 km. Increase in pore pressure was sufficient to induce seismicity migration. However,
480 velocity and duration of the migration were such that they suggest a process analogous to fluid in-
481 jection. The drying up of the "Chez-les-Roux" cold water springs (Thouvenot et al. (1998); altitude
482 600m) during the aftershock sequence and the overflow of the Bromines thermal spring (located in
483 the Vuache Fault, at 500 m altitude at this place) suggest that a gravitational collapse of the highest
484 part of the fluid column occurred from day 11 after the mainshock, pressurising the deepest part of the

Figure 18. SE-NW vertical cross-section, along Vuache Fault strike, showing the M5.3 1996 Epagny mainshock (black star) and its aftershocks (coloured dots). The colour of the dots indicates the earthquake occurrence time from the mainshock. The coloured solid lines represent the tops of the main sedimentary formations inferred from seismic profiles (Charroy et al. 2026). Green: Urgonian limestones; blue: Tithonian limestones; red: granitic bedrock). Brown dashed lines represent the decollement levels of the thrusts. Blue dashed lines represent the fluid flow. Shaded blue area represents the approximate extension of the fluid reservoir.

485 aquifer (Figure 18). Therefore, in this model the earthquake migration evidenced from day 11 is not
 486 directly due to the diffusion of a perturbation of pressure from the mainshock, but mostly to the grav-
 487 itational collapse of the fluid column induced by the improved connectivity between two reservoirs,
 488 one shallow (Urgonian limestones) and one deeper, in the fractured Vuache Fault. The high migration
 489 velocity and limited earthquake magnitude suggest channeling along this fault.

490 The contrast in permeability between the fractures and the surrounding rock allows the hydraulic
 491 pressure to be maintained in the Vuache Fault. The permeability appears to be strongly anisotropic,
 492 with its component transverse to the Vuache Fault being far lower than its longitudinal component.
 493 From the study of the aftershock sequence, the Vuache Fault appears to be a longitudinal drain and a
 494 transverse hydraulic barrier. This explains the absence of aftershocks in the south-western compart-
 495 ment from day 11 (Figure 13). We however cannot rule out the possibility that fluid leakage may occur

Figure 19. AVV measured (in %, in blue) and cumulative number of earthquakes (in red) as a function of time between 2012 (installation time of the station) and 2021, at the OGME station (1-2Hz, single-station, NE cross-component). The vertical dashed black line indicates the occurrence time of the M2.7 Meythet earthquake on April 6th, 2013, whose epicentre was located approximately 500 m north of the OGME station, at about 2 km depth.

496 without producing earthquakes, in ductile and water-soluble formations such as Triassic gypsum. In
 497 the last days, earthquakes reached the base of the sedimentary sequence (Figure 14).

498 **6.6 Observation of a post-seismic recovery by using seismic velocity variations - consequences**
 499 **for the deep aquifer**

500 Analysis of the temporal variation in seismic velocities before and following the M2.7 earthquake
 501 in Meythet on April 6th, 2013, at the Meythet RAP station (OGME), reveals a post-seismic velocity
 502 variation (Figure 19): velocities, which were low before the earthquake, tended to rise slowly after
 503 May 2013, while maintaining the seasonal variations also observed at the OGEP station (Figure 6).

504 This post-seismic velocity increase strongly suggests that hydraulic pressure and fracture volume
 505 gradually decrease beneath OGME after 2013. This is consistent with the decreasing rate of the low-
 506 magnitude earthquakes detected at the OGME station (Figures 19 and H.1). These figures also show
 507 that earthquake swarms are only triggered when the seismic velocity is low (AVV typically -0.2 to
 508 -0.4%), that is, when overpressure is above some threshold (typically 0.4 to 0.8 MPa from equation
 509 (14), which corresponds to an increase in the water column height of 40 to 80m).

510 Contrary to what is measured at OGEP, where the seasonal variation in seismic velocity is at zero-
 511 mean (and therefore inflow equals outflow), the variation measured at OGME shows that outflow is

512 greater than inflow between 2013 and 2020. This suggests that the M2.7 earthquake in Meythet in
 513 2013 may have been caused by the rupture of a hydraulic barrier, leading to the progressive drainage
 514 of a reservoir. Aftershocks of this earthquake reached the depth of the Triassic gypsum (Figure H.2)
 515 and may eventually flow in this permeable layer. The fact that OGEP and OGME show different seis-
 516 mic velocity variation patterns tends to show that, at depth, the two sites were relatively independent
 517 hydraulically at least between 2013 and 2019.

518 Figure 19 illustrates a striking feature of these velocity variations: drainage occurs with two dif-
 519 ferent characteristic times. Faster seasonal variations have a characteristic time of about 10 days (10^6 s,
 520 Figure 16), and the post-seismic variation has a characteristic time of about 3 years (10^8 s), i.e. two
 521 orders of magnitude larger.

522 Rorabaugh (1964) and Rorabaugh & Simons (1966) have shown that the flow rate per unit width
 523 Q of an aquifer during its charge or discharge can be expressed as a function of time as :

$$Q(t) = Q_0 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \quad (15)$$

524 where Q_0 is the flow rate per unit width at time $t = 0$, and τ is the characteristic time of the aquifer.
 525 These authors have shown that

$$\tau = \left(\frac{2a}{\pi}\right)^2 \frac{1}{D} \quad (16)$$

526 where a is the characteristic dimension of the aquifer, and D the hydraulic diffusivity.

527 The characteristic time of the aquifer being proportional to a^2/D , the two values found here for τ
 528 correspond to two different processes:

529 - the seasonal variation ($a^2/D \approx 10^6$ s) represents the charge/discharge of a relatively smaller
 530 (typically $a \approx 1$ km) volume and/or of a larger diffusivity (typically $D \approx 1$ m²/s), likely under the
 531 effect of water table fluctuations;

532 - the post-seismic variation is the discharge/drainage of a larger volume and/or of lower diffusivity,
 533 such as $a^2/D \approx 10^8$ s; in a fractured volume, the stimulated volume increases with the pressure
 534 perturbation, but diffusivity often decreases with increasing volume (see, e.g., Javani et al. (2025), and
 535 references therein). At constant diffusivity, the characteristic dimension of the volume stimulated by
 536 the M2.7 2013 earthquake would be 10 times larger than the one concerned by the seasonal pressure
 537 variations.

538 **6.7 Spatial distribution of the seismicity, coupling between thrust and strike-slip deformation,**
539 **and hydromechanical coupling**

540 These results tend to show that the seismicity of the Epagny-Annecy region is due to the activation
541 of the Vuache Fault under the effect of fluid pressurisation. Earthquake locations are confined in a
542 limited volume. This one may be linked with the geometry of the aquifer and the confinement of
543 the fluids, vertically between impermeable layers (particularly molasse upwards), and laterally, to the
544 southwest by the vertical offset of the Vuache Fault. To the northwest (La Balme-de-Sillingy), this
545 boundary seems to correspond to the location where the Mandallaz thrust applies a higher normal
546 stress than elsewhere on the Vuache Fault (see, for example, Thouvenot et al. (1998)), inhibiting fluid
547 propagation and induced seismicity. The same mechanism can be invoked to understand the seismicity
548 to the south-east of the mainshock of 1996 (aftershocks and seismicity 1995-2025). This area has
549 been studied extensively by Courboulex et al. (1999), who showed that this mainshock consisted of
550 two sub-events between which the rupture propagated from the north-west to the south-east, in the
551 vicinity of a volume of rock without aftershocks highlighted by Thouvenot et al. (1998) (Figure 3).
552 This volume lies between the two fault segments, and the aftershocks only developed at the eastern
553 boundary of this volume from the 11th day (Figures 9 and 13) from the mainshock occurrence time,
554 showing a remarkable alignment and migration connecting the two fault segments. Most of the largest
555 earthquakes occurring along the Vuache Fault at Epagny after the 1996 sequence were located at the
556 south-eastern end of the 1996 aftershock zone (Figures 13 and 20). Especially, this place was the site
557 of the M2.7 Meythet earthquake (the strongest earthquake since the 1996 crisis), which was followed
558 by the remarkable seismic velocity increase evidenced at the OGME station (Figure 19). The volume
559 surrounding the M2.7 Meythet earthquake therefore may act as a more resistant barrier that breaks
560 when the fluid pressure reaches a sufficiently high level, increasing the local permeability in the fault
561 zone.

562 This volume can be linked to the existence of a deformed zone, visible in seismic profiles (Charroy
563 et al. 2026) and reported on some geological structural maps (e.g., Chelle-Michou et al. (2017); Bren-
564 tini (2018); Guglielmetti et al. (2022)), which manifests itself on the surface as secondary topographic
565 highs (the Crêts and Machurettes hills, Figure 3). This deformed zone has been formed later than the
566 main thrust and the Vuache Fault, when these ones became locked under the weight of the overlying
567 compartment. This weight tends to compress the rock horizontally, normally to its fractures in the
568 Vuache Fault zone, increasing its strength and reducing its permeability. This heterogeneity of normal
569 stress and permeability seems to be inherent to the deformation process, which creates both thrust
570 and strike-slip faults. It is conducive to the formation of reservoirs closed by less permeable barriers.
571 When the fluids are pressurized, fluid transfer may occur suddenly by stronger magnitude earthquakes

Figure 20. Map of the Annecy Molasse Basin showing the cartographic trace of the Vuache Fault (dashed blue line), the M5.3 1996 Epagny mainshock (large dark blue disk), and the locations of all earthquakes $M \geq 1.2$ between 1995 and 2025 (coloured dots, with radius proportional to the earthquake magnitude). The red square highlights the M2.7 2013 Meythet earthquake, and the red circle represents the first event of the January 9th, 2024 earthquake cascade (see Figure 5 for the time distribution of these earthquakes).

572 through these less permeable barriers, which act as valves; this recalls the fault valve model of Sibson
 573 (1981, 1984). Aftershocks locations show that at least a part of this transfer is horizontal – fluids are
 574 confined beneath the impermeable molasse and above the Lower-Middle Jurassic marls. We can de-
 575 duce that this valve separates two reservoirs: an upstream reservoir directly connected to the surface,

576 which reacts most directly to rainfall, and a downstream reservoir that fills when permeability through
577 the valve is sufficient. This mechanism may explain the recovery pattern observed at OGME between
578 2013 and 2019, where fluid pressure decreased after the M2.7 earthquake. The downstream reservoir
579 can therefore fill slowly. Its pressurisation might eventually be responsible for the historical seismicity
580 reported for Annecy (notably the seismic swarms in 1839, 1879 and 1955) - though the locations are
581 uncertain. However, we cannot exclude that another, aseismic and larger, reservoir exists.

582 The coupling between the two deformation processes (thrust and strike-slip faulting) can therefore
583 create variability in normal stress along the strike-slip fault, and favourable conditions for the forma-
584 tion of reservoirs in fractured volumes. Fluids under pressure are also coupled with the reservoir rock.
585 The coupled system can evolve through pseudo-periodic behaviour: a stronger earthquake can occur
586 each time the pressure is high enough to break the reservoir rock. This process segments seismicity
587 and can control the earthquake magnitude distribution. Figure 5 shows that locally the trend is now
588 towards a progressive weakening of the rock mass concerned, as the magnitude of the largest events
589 decreases, and the intervals between these events also decrease. It is therefore likely that the damage
590 process currently outweighs the fault sealing process, and that permeability is increasing at this lo-
591 cation. However, this process of local weakening of the Vuache Fault in the Epagny basin probably
592 contributes to increasing stress on more resistant rock volumes of the fault, for example under the
593 weight of the upper compartment of the Mandallaz thrust.

594 **7 CONCLUSION**

595 The objective of this work was to better understand the seismicity of the Epagny-Annecy region,
596 an alpine foreland area located between the geological Jura and subalpine massifs where an M5.3
597 earthquake occurred in 1996. Some results of this search may eventually be used in similar contexts,
598 or compared with others.

599 The analysis of the 1995-2024 earthquake time series in the Epagny basin shows that the seismicity
600 rate after the 1996 M5.3 earthquake decreased steadily over 16 years, following an Omori law with
601 p close to 1. Later, swarms of earthquakes occurred in 2013, 2021 and 2024, including an M2.7
602 earthquake in 2013.

603 Detailed analysis of the spatio-temporal distribution of aftershocks following the 1996 M5.3 earth-
604 quake shows a migration of their hypocentres, particularly from 10 days after the date of the main
605 shock. This migration, the drying up of sources located at higher altitudes and the increase in the flow
606 rate of the Bromines thermal spring located at the foot of the relief are consistent with a reservoir
607 model, pressurised by gravity via a hydraulic column, whose permeability increased during the first
608 phase of the aftershocks (first 10 days), causing the column to collapse. This increase in permeability

609 then allows the diffusion of fluids with an estimated hydraulic diffusivity of about 2 m²/s during the
610 second phase of aftershocks.

611 Calculations of temporal variations in seismic velocities in the Epagny basin show seasonal vari-
612 ations and a correlation with rainfall. These temporal variations in seismic velocities are produced by
613 variations in the volume and length of fractures under the effect of fluid pressure variations. Inversion
614 of these velocity variations shows that their maximum is located between 1 and 2 km depth. The fact
615 that they are seasonal and correlated with rainfall shows that the deep pressurised aquifer is connected
616 to the surface. This correlation with rainfall makes it possible to calculate a time lag of 10 days. This
617 allows us to estimate a value for hydraulic diffusivity (1 m²/s), which is compatible with the value (2
618 m²/s) deduced from the aftershocks of the 1996 M5.3 earthquake.

619 After the M2.7 earthquake in Meythet in 2013, seismic velocities tended to increase and seismicity
620 rates to decrease, while showing seasonal variations, which is consistent with a decrease in average
621 fluid pressure at depth. The characteristic time (3 to 5 years) over which this decrease occurs is two
622 orders of magnitude greater than the time lag between rainfall and velocity variations, implying a
623 larger volume involved and/or lower diffusivity.

624 Thus, while the magnitude and mechanism at the focus of the 1996 M5.3 earthquake show that the
625 initiation of the process is indeed tectonic in origin, the length of the Omori decay of its aftershocks,
626 their spatio-temporal distribution showing migration, the variations in source flows according to their
627 altitude, the existence of repeated swarms, the temporal and seasonal variations in velocity and their
628 relationship to seismicity show that the continuation of this seismicity is linked to the pressurisation
629 of fluids in a deep, fractured aquifer connected to the surface.

630 The process of horizontal shortening of the foreland sedimentary cover during the collision of the
631 African and Indo-European plates in the Alps leads to the formation of thrust and strike-slip faults.
632 When a thrust becomes locked under the effect of its weight and the friction it causes, the shortening
633 continues by forming other thrusts behind it. All of these thrusts delimit basins that can be reservoirs
634 of meteoric fluids if the sedimentary series includes, as in the geological Jura and subalpine massifs,
635 aquifer formations such as fractured limestones, which outcrop at the top of the thrust folds. These
636 reservoirs can be seismogenic when tectonic stresses and fluid pressure are sufficient in the strike-slip
637 faults. This case can be quite common around the Alps and other collision ranges, and may explain
638 part of the shallow seismicity of the foreland.

639 **8 DATA AVAILABILITY**

640 Seismological data used in this article are available from the public domain EPOS-France network
641 through the FDSN standard webservice (<https://ws.resif.fr/> and <https://www.fdsn.org/webservices/>).

642 Networks are 'FR' for EPOS-France-RESIF, and 'RA' for EPOS-France-RAP.

643 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

644 **Appendices**645 **APPENDIX A: HISTORICAL SEISMICITY IN ANNECY**

Earthquake nb	Date	Intensity
1	1572	
2	1833/05/13	3
3	1839/08/07	
4	1839/08/08	
5	1839/08/09	
6	1839/08/11	7
7	1839/08/16	
8	1839/08/21	
9	1839/08/23	
10	1839/08/27	
11	1840/03/22	
12	1847/03/05	4
13	1879/07/25	
14	1879/07/26	
15	1879/09/27	3.5 Swarm
16	1879/10/15	
17	1955/09/10	4

646

Table A1: Historical seismicity in Annecy. Data extracted from SisFrance, BRGM, EDF, IRSN, 2025.

647 **APPENDIX B: SENSITIVITY KERNELS USED IN THE INVERSION OF SEISMIC**
 648 **VELOCITY VARIATIONS**

649

Figure B.1: P and S-wave seismic velocity (from Capar et al. (2015); resp. blue and red line) in km/s, and density (green line), as a function of depth below the surface in the Epagny basin.

650

Figure B.2: Sensitivity kernels computed (Herrmann 2013) from the S-wave velocity and density models of the Epagny basin (Figure B.1). C is the Rayleigh wave phase velocity and V_s the S-wave velocity. Depth is below the surface.

Figure B.3: Restitution index as a function of depth below the surface.

652 **APPENDIX C: REGIONAL GEOLOGICAL CROSS-SECTIONS**

653

Figure C.1: Regional geological cross-section following the profile A in Figure 1. From Beck et al. (1998).

Figure D.1: Map of the Annecy-Epagny Molasse Basin showing the M5.3 1996 Epagny mainshock (black star), its aftershocks (coloured dots), the profiles used for the cross-sections (b) and (c) (Figure D.2; red dashed lines). Refer to Figure 3 for geological structures. The colour of the dots indicates the earthquake depth.

656

657

Figure D.2: (b) SW-NE vertical cross-section, normal to the Vuache Fault strike. (c) SE-NW vertical cross-section, along Vuache Fault strike. Cross-sections show the M5.3 1996 Epagny mainshock (large deep blue disk (b), star (c)) and its aftershocks (coloured dots; colour represents the earthquake occurrence time from the mainshock; green star represents the largest M4.3 aftershock). The coloured horizontal lines represent the tops of the main sedimentary formations inferred from seismic profiles (Charroy et al. 2026). Green: Urgonian limestones; blue: Tithonian limestones; pink: Triassic gypsum; red: granitic bedrock. Brown dashed lines represent the decollement levels of the thrusts. In (b), SW thick black dashed line represents the cartographic trace of the Vuache Fault, inferred from the geological map; NE thick black dashed line represents the faults limiting the Epagny basin, inferred from Guglielmetti et al. (2022). Light black dashed line represents the trace of the mean active fault plane inferred from the aftershocks locations. Light red dashed line represents the approximate limits of the Vuache Fault damaged zone. In (c), the vertical light dashed line represents the (b) SW-NE cross-section profile.

658 **APPENDIX E: COMPLETENESS MAGNITUDE**

659

Figure E.1: Cumulative number of earthquakes as a function of magnitude. Completeness magnitude is $M_c \approx 1.2$, and $b \approx 0.9$.

660 **APPENDIX F: SEASONAL VARIATIONS OF SEISMICITY**

661

Figure F.1: Number of earthquakes ($M \geq M_c$) as a function of the month of the year, from 1997 to 2024, located in the Epagny area.

662

Figure F.2: Number of earthquakes as a function of the month of the year, from 2012 to 2019, detected from the records of the RAP accelerometric station OGME (Meythet). Earthquakes were local small-magnitude events, the waveforms of which were similar to Figure 10. The large number of earthquakes detected in April corresponds to the small-magnitude aftershocks of the April 6th, 2013 M2.7 Meythet earthquake.

663 **APPENDIX G: ABSENCE OF EARTHQUAKE MIGRATION DURING THE FIRST 10**
664 **DAYS AFTER THE MAINSHOCK**

665

Figure G.1: Distance between aftershocks and mainshock, in km, as a function of time in days for the first 10 days after the mainshock date.

666 **APPENDIX H: MEYTHET M2.7 POST-SEISMIC EARTHQUAKE RATE, SEISMIC**
 667 **VELOCITY VARIATIONS, AND EARTHQUAKE LOCATIONS**

668 **H1 Post-M2.7 seismic velocity and earthquake rate variations**

669

Figure H.1: Computed AVV (in blue) and earthquake rate (in red) as a function of time between 2012 and 2021, at the OGME station (Meythet). The vertical dashed black line indicates the occurrence time of the M2.7 Meythet earthquake on April 6th, 2013, whose epicentre was located approximately 500 m north of the OGME station.

670 **H2 Pre- and post-M2.7 earthquake locations**

671

Figure H.2: SE-NW vertical cross-section along the Vuache Fault strike, showing the main geological features and the earthquake locations (coloured dots) during the June 2012 to June 2013 time period, comprising the M2.7 Meythet earthquake (April 6th, 2013; green square). The location of the M5.3 1996 Epagny mainshock is represented by a black star. The colour of the dots indicates the earthquake occurrence time from the mainshock. The coloured horizontal lines represent the tops of the main sedimentary formations inferred from seismic profiles (Charroy et al. 2026). Green: Urganian limestones; blue: Tithonian limestones; red: granitic bedrock). Brown dashed lines represent the decollement levels of the thrusts. Black triangles represent the location of the OGME and OGEP accelerometric stations.

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